

**Project SOP D-JRP17-
WP1.SOP4 – Standard
Operating procedure for
Bacteriological diagnosis
Workpackage 1**

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STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE FOR BACTERIOLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS

Scope

This procedure describes the classical bacteriological method for isolation of *Brucella* spp. in animal (frogs, reptiles, foxes, marine mammals, wild ruminants, bats, fishes, rodents, squirrel, hedgehog, badgers, others in the scope of IDEMBRU) and environmental (water and soil) samples.

Culture media

Several non-selective (enriched or non-enriched) solid agar media can be used for *Brucella* spp. isolation, such as Tryptic Soya Agar (TSA), Tryptose Agar (TA), *Brucella* Medium Base (BMB), Blood Agar Base No.2 (BAB), and Columbia Agar (CA).

Farrell's and CITA media are the recommended selective media for brucellae first isolation (Brucellosis infection with *Brucella abortus*, *B. melitensis* and *B. suis*, OIE/WOAH Chapter 3.1.4.). The sensitivity of culture increases significantly by the simultaneous use of Farrell and CITA media.

Farrell's medium can be prepared with any of the previously identified non-selective solid agar medium. The media should be heated and fully dissolved with no powder on the walls of the vessel before autoclaving at 121°C for 20 minutes. Cool to 56-60°C in a water bath, and add 5% sterile calf serum. To 1 litre of agar add polymyxin B sulphate (5000 units = 5 mg); bacitracin (25 000 units = 25 mg); natamycin (50 mg); nalidixic acid (5 mg); nystatin (100 000 units); vancomycin (20 mg). A corresponding freeze-dried antibiotic supplement is available commercially (OXOID). Follow the supplier's instructions to reconstitute (aseptically in sterile diluent) and use the antibiotics and antifungals. The plates containing medium can be kept at 5 ± 3°C up to eight days.

CITA medium is prepared with BAB supplemented with 5% sterile calf serum and vancomycin (20 mg/L), colistin methanesulfonate (7.5 mg/L), nitrofurantoin (10 mg/L), nystatin (100 000 IU/L), and amphotericin B (4 mg/L). This antibiotic mixture can be prepared as follows:

- Weigh vancomycin, colistin and nystatin in the same 50 mL sterile container, then rehydrate the mixture with 10 mL of a 1:1 solution of absolute methanol in sterile purified water.
- Weigh nitrofurantoin in a sterile tube and dissolve it with 1 mL of 0.1 M NaOH solution (sterilised previously by filtration through a 0.22 µm filter).
- Weigh 10 mg of amphotericin B in a 20 mL sterile container and dissolve with 1 mL dimethyl sulphoxide. Once fully dissolved (5–10 minutes are required), add 9 mL of 10 mM sterile phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (pH=7.2 ± 0.2). The final concentration of amphotericin B would be 1 mg/mL; a total of 4 mL of this solution is required for 1 liter of medium. The remaining Amphotericin B suspension can be kept at 5°C ± 3°C for several days for further uses.

Culture procedure

Sampling conditions and sample treatment should be performed according to OHEJP-JRP19-WP1-SOP1 (Guidelines for sample collection and treatment).

Some *Brucella* strains are CO₂-dependent for growth. Therefore, to increase the chances of isolating brucellae, each specimen should be inoculated on at least four plates, half being incubated in a normal atmosphere, half being incubated in an atmosphere enriched with 5-10 % CO₂.

1. Tissues and/or Organs

- Tissues should be previously cut in small pieces and macerated and ground as completely as possible, if necessary, in presence of PBS pH 7.2 \pm 0.2 in a proportion of 1/2 to 1/5 in order to get a suspension of adequate density for culture.
- Inoculate 0.2-0.4 mL of the homogenous suspension onto the first plate of each selective media, and spread with a plate spreader for the second plate.
- Incubate the plates at 37 \pm 2°C, two in a normal atmosphere, the other two in an atmosphere with 5-10 % CO₂.
- *Brucella* colonies generally become visible after 3-5 days. After that time, it is advisable to routinely examine the plates at least up to the 14th day of culture, before cultures be discarded as negative. Suspected colonies should be picked and inoculate in non-selective medium for further identification.

2. Swabs

- Dry swab is withdrawn aseptically from the protecting tube or envelope and rehydrated with 1 mL of PBS pH 7.2 \pm 0.2, if necessary. Once rehydrated, the swab should be rolled over onto 2 plates of each selective (or non selective) culture media.
- Swab with transport medium should be rolled over onto 2 plates of each selective (or non selective) culture media.
- Incubate the plates at 37 \pm 2°C, two in a normal atmosphere, the other two in an atmosphere with 5-10 % CO₂, and check for *Brucella* colonies after 3-5 days, examining routinely the plates at least up to the 14th day of culture, before cultures be discarded as negative. Suspected colonies should be picked and inoculate in non-selective medium for further identification.

3. Genital secretions or semen.

- Genital secretions or semen does not need any additional preparation for bacteriology. Place about 0.2-0.4 mL of the sample with sterile pipette on the first plate of each selective (or non-selective) culture media. Spread with seeder, and perform seeding by exhaustion on the second plate.
- Incubate the plates at 37 \pm 2°C, two in a normal atmosphere, the other two in an atmosphere with 5-10 % CO₂, and check for *Brucella* colonies after 3-5 days, examining routinely the plates at least up to the 14th day of culture, before cultures be discarded as negative. Suspected colonies should be picked and inoculate in non-selective medium for further identification.

4. Environmental samples

- Water samples (ideally 0.25 - 1 liter) will be concentrated using 0.22 μ m filters or concentrating pipettes. After filtration, the filter should be suspended into PBS pH 7.2 overnight before plating selective or non-selective media.
- Soil samples will be performed in a depth between 0-1 cm, as first line sampling strategy. For direct cultivation of *Brucella* spp. from soil, 2-5 g of samples could be thoroughly homogenized in 5 mL of PBS pH 7.2. A serial dilution in PBS from 10⁰ to 10⁻³ could be done to decrease the level of potential contamination and 0.1-0.2 mL will be plated onto selective or non selective media.
- Incubate the plates at 37 \pm 2°C, two in a normal atmosphere, the other two in an atmosphere with 5-10 % CO₂, and check for *Brucella* colonies after 3-5 days, examining routinely the plates at least up to the 14th day of culture, before cultures be discarded as negative. Suspected colonies should be picked and inoculate in non-selective medium for further identification.

***Brucella* spp. identification and typing**

For the identification at the level of species and typification of biovars, there is not a single laboratory test, being several tests, whose interpretation as a whole allows to establish the corresponding

differences. The differentiation of *Brucella* species is based on the morphological analysis of the colonies, on biochemical tests (urease, catalase and oxidase) and on the lysis by specific phages (Tb, Wb, Iz and R/C). The species of *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus* and *B. suis* are subdivided into biovars, according to four tests: the requirement in CO₂, the production of H₂S, the sensitivity to bacteriostatic dyes (Tionin, Fucsin and Safranin) and agglutination by monospecific sera anti-A, -M and -R.

Suspicious colonies of *Brucella* are seeded into a non-selective culture medium in duplicate and incubated in a normal atmosphere and in an atmosphere enriched with 5% CO₂, at 37°C for 72 hours.

Smooth *Brucella* spp. cultures have a tendency to undergo variation during growth, especially with subcultures, and dissociate to R forms. Verifying the colonial morphology of a culture is essential before performing any identification and biotyping test, since agglutination, phage lysis and dye susceptibility for growth may be altered with the R forms of naturally S *Brucella* strains.

More information is available on the EURL website:

[Brucella culture and genus identification | EURL \(anses.fr\)](#)

[Brucella bacteriological typing | EURL \(anses.fr\)](#)

[Training videos for brucellosis | EURL \(anses.fr\)](#)